

[Click here to view linked References](#)

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29

ASSESSMENT OF POST-LIQUEFACTION CONSOLIDATION SETTLEMENT

Anna Chiaradonna¹, Anna d'Onofrio², Emilio Bilotta³

¹Research Fellow, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, University of Napoli Federico II, Naples, Italy, anna.chiaradonna@unina.it

²Associate Professor, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, University of Napoli Federico II, Naples, Italy, donofrio@unina.it

³Associate Professor, Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering, University of Napoli Federico II, Naples, Italy, bilotta@unina.it

Corresponding author:

Anna Chiaradonna

Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering

University of Napoli Federico II

Via Claudio, 21

80125 Naples

Italy

phone: +39 081 7685916

e-mail: anna.chiaradonna@unina.it

30 **ABSTRACT**

31 This paper presents a simplified procedure for the evaluation of the free-field consolidation settlement induced by
32 liquefaction, using the results of 1D site response analysis in effective stress and simplified approach based on empirical
33 chart. The excess pore water pressures generated by the seismic action are generated by both a simple stress-based model
34 implemented on a non-linear dynamic analysis and a simplified relationship between the safety factor against liquefaction
35 and the excess pore pressure. The post-cyclic settlement is finally calculated on the obtained distribution of excess pore
36 water pressure along the soil column.

37 The proposed method has been used to estimate the consolidation settlements in a centrifuge test and in well-documented
38 case histories of widespread liquefaction: Treasure Island and Marina District after the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake. The
39 results have been compared to the measured settlements and to the values obtained by previous studies. It is shown that
40 the proposed approach leads to a much more accurate estimate of the post-liquefaction consolidation settlement, with just
41 a little increase of the calculation effort.

42
43 **Keywords:** liquefaction; excess pore pressure; post-liquefaction settlement; in-situ testing; 1D seismic soil response.

44 1. INTRODUCTION

45 Liquefaction-induced ground deformations have caused significant damage to engineered structures and lifelines during
46 past earthquakes (1999 Kocaeli, Turkey earthquake; 2011 Christchurch, New Zealand earthquake; 2012 Emilia, Italy
47 earthquake, 2018 Palu, Indonesia earthquake). For the preliminary assessment of damage, a simplified estimation of
48 liquefaction-induced ground settlement still remains the most valuable tool in seismic design of geotechnical facilities.
49 Recently, Bray and Macedo (2017) suggested computing such a settlement as the sum of three components: (i) one due
50 to the formation of sediment ejecta; (ii) a shear-induced component caused by pre-existing shear stresses; (iii) a post-
51 liquefaction component induced by volumetric consolidation. Even though in many cases the first two components may
52 be the most relevant, the state-of-practice for estimating liquefaction-induced ground settlement is still largely based on
53 empirical procedures developed to estimate only the third component (post-liquefaction consolidation settlement) in free-
54 field (1D) conditions (e.g. Tokimatsu and Seed 1987; Ishihara and Yoshimine 1992; Zhang et al. 2002). With these
55 procedures, volumetric strains resulting from the dissipation of pore-water pressures are correlated via simple charts with
56 relative density (D_r) and a factor of safety against liquefaction (FS) for clean sands. These correlations have the great
57 advantage of being easy to use. On the other hand, they are based on laboratory test results on specific sands (Fuji River
58 sand in the method by Ishihara and Yoshimine 1992 used also in the one by Zhang et al. 2002) and their use on sands
59 having different grading and mineralogy may lead to unsatisfactory predictions. Moreover, Cubrinovski et al. (2018)
60 recently highlighted that effective stress analysis is crucial to identify the whole system response of the deposit, involving
61 dynamic interaction between layers and empirical charts may be oversimplified.

62 On the other hand, Ramirez et al. (2018) compare the predictive capabilities of common numerical platforms and most
63 popular classes of advanced soil constitutive models (multi-yield and bounding surface) with the results of a centrifuge
64 experiment simulating seismic site response in a layered liquefiable soil. The results of this study show that all models,
65 although capable of reproducing accelerations and excess pore pressures, perform poorly in terms of volumetric
66 settlements. This implies that the assessment of post-liquefaction consolidation settlement is still an issue in the numerical
67 modelling of the seismic response of liquefiable soils.

68 A possible compromise between sophisticated and empirical procedures for the estimation of settlement can be found in
69 dynamic analyses, where simplifications can be introduced in modelling both the geometrical scheme and the soil
70 behaviour, but the key mechanism of the pore pressure build-up is simulated. In this paper, this approach has been
71 followed: a method is proposed to evaluate the post-liquefaction consolidation settlement resulting from the dissipation
72 of excess pore pressures using non-linear, effective stress numerical analyses in 1-D conditions. A simplified model is
73 adopted for the generation and dissipation of excess pore water pressure, which requires the definition of two curves: the

74 cyclic resistance curve and the pore pressure ratio vs. the normalized number of cycles (Chiaradonna et al. 2018a). The
 75 model is already implemented in the non-linear code SCOSSA (Tropeano et al. 2016) and validated on centrifuge tests
 76 and well-instrumented test sites, as detailed by Chiaradonna (2016) and Tropeano et al. (2019). In the code, the soil profile
 77 is modelled as a system of consistent lumped masses, connected by viscous dampers and springs with hysteretic
 78 behaviour. The non-linear and dissipative behaviour of the soil is defined by the shear modulus degradation, $G/G_0(\gamma)$ and
 79 damping, $D(\gamma)$ curves, which are described by the MKZ model (Matasovic and Vucetic 1993) and by the modified Masing
 80 rules (Phillips and Hashash 2009). The code permits to select both options of total and effective stress analyses, this latter
 81 in total undrained or partial drained condition. It is worth noticing that, although it is known (Santisi d'Avila et al. 2012,
 82 2013) that multi-axial stress states may induce strength reduction of the material and larger damping, hence affecting the
 83 calculated excess pore pressures, the effect of three-component ground motion is neglected in the code and unidirectional
 84 propagation of one-component polarized shear waves has been modelled.

85 An alternative and simpler methodology to the previous based on the 1D dynamic analysis, is estimate the pore water
 86 pressure distribution using simplified relationship between the safety factor against liquefaction and the pore pressure
 87 ratio (Marcuson et al. 1990; Iwasaki et al. 1984; Chiaradonna and Flora 2019). The relationship proposed by Chiaradonna
 88 and Flora (2019) are here adopted to generate a pore pressure ratio profile.

89 The post-cyclic consolidation settlement is then computed via the oedometric method. It is worth highlighting that the
 90 paper proposes a simplified procedure that, in evaluating only the volumetric settlement caused by consolidation, may
 91 help in getting the order of magnitude of the observed overall effect leading to a better estimate, if compared to the
 92 existing simplified methods.

93 The described procedure is first applied to a centrifuge test where the value of post-cyclic consolidation settlement was
 94 measured. Then, two well-documented cases histories are analyzed, where measurements of liquefaction-induced free
 95 field settlements are available, comparing the results with those obtained using the existing empirical methods.

96 2. POST-LIQUEFACTION CONSOLIDATION SETTLEMENT

97 The post-cyclic consolidation of loose soil deposits is caused by the volume changes due to the dissipation of earthquake-
 98 induced excess pore water pressures. In free-field conditions, if the stratigraphy can be assumed horizontally layered, it
 99 is reasonable to assume that little or no lateral displacements occur after the earthquake, such that the volumetric strain
 100 will be equal or close to the vertical strain. Therefore, in the following it will be assumed that, in free-field conditions,
 101 the dissipation of excess pore pressure induces a post-cyclic consolidation settlement that can be computed as follows:

$$102 \quad w = \sum_i^n \frac{\Delta \sigma_i'}{E_{oed,i}} \Delta z_i \quad (1)$$

103 where $\Delta\sigma'_i$ is the increment of vertical effective stress coming from the dissipation of excess pore pressure Δu in the i -th
 104 layer of the n layers in which the soil profile was divided; $E_{oed,i}$ is the constrained or oedometric modulus of the generic
 105 layer i , and Δz_i is its thickness.

106 As well known, E_{oed} may be related to the Young modulus, E' , being usually $E_{oed}=1.2E$ to $1.5E'$. For loose sands, in the
 107 following the value $E_{oed}=1.2E'$ will be assumed. On the other hand, the Young modulus can be calculated from CPT
 108 results as:

$$109 \quad E' = \beta_{E_{oed}} \cdot q_c \quad (2)$$

110 and consequently

$$111 \quad E_{oed} = 1.2E' = \alpha_{E_{oed}} \cdot q_c \quad (3)$$

112 where q_c is the cone tip resistance measured in CPT, $\beta_{E_{oed}}$ is an empirical coefficient that depends on soil grading and
 113 relative density and $\alpha_{E_{oed}} = 1.2\beta_{E_{oed}}$. In this study, following the suggestions by Meyerhof and Fellenius (1985) for the
 114 case of normally consolidated sands, the value $\beta_{E_{oed}}=3$ will be assumed, but any other value may be used if different
 115 experimental evidences (e.g., comparison of laboratory and in situ testing results) are available. However, it must be
 116 emphasized that after liquefaction the consolidation takes place at low effective confining stresses, in a slurry that initially
 117 behaves as an under-consolidated soil, and therefore the low value of $\beta_{E_{oed}}$ here suggested seems reasonable. Then, it
 118 follows that:

$$119 \quad E_{oed} = 3.6 \cdot q_c \quad (4)$$

120 Even though equation (4) expresses an empirical correlation, it has been calibrated on a large number of data from
 121 different soils. Once the oedometric stiffness is known, the distribution of the pore pressure increments (and therefore
 122 that of the effective stress increments) with depth has to be evaluated.

123 The calculation of $\Delta\sigma'_i$ is obtained by a 1D dynamic analysis in effective stress, through a simplified pore pressure model,
 124 ‘PWP model’, described in deep detail in Chiaradonna et al. (2018a). The ‘PWP model’ permits to compare the irregular
 125 time-history of shear stress induced by earthquake with the soil liquefaction resistance, evaluated in stress-controlled
 126 cyclic laboratory tests. The comparison is expressed through the so called ‘damage parameter’, which can be computed
 127 for any loading pattern. The damage parameter, κ , is an incremental function of the applied load that considers the cyclic
 128 strength of the soil. This latter is expressed in terms of cyclic resistance curve, analytically described by the equation
 129 (Chiaradonna et al. 2018a):

$$130 \quad \frac{(CRR - CSR_r)}{(CSR_r - CSR_i)} = \left(\frac{N_r}{N_L} \right)^{1/\alpha} \quad (5)$$

131 where CRR is the shear stress amplitude normalized by the initial effective confining pressure; N_L is the number of cycles
 132 to reach liquefaction condition, CSR_t is the ordinate of the curve related to 15 cycles ($N_r = 15$ is usually adopted as a
 133 reference number of cycles). The parameters CSR_t and α can be evaluated from the cyclic resistance curve obtained from
 134 laboratory tests, being CSR_t the asymptotic value of cyclic stress ratio as the number of cycles tends to infinite, and α is a
 135 coefficient related to the slope of the cyclic resistance curve in a log–log scale. If it is not possible to estimate the threshold
 136 value CSR_t from the experimental cyclic resistance curve, it can be estimated from the “backbone” shear stress–strain curve of
 137 the soil, considering the shear stress, τ_t , corresponding to the volumetric threshold strain, γ_v , and computing CSR_t as ratio
 138 between τ_t and the initial effective stress state. The latter is commonly assumed as the shear strain corresponding to the onset of
 139 pore pressure build-up observed during resonant column or torsional shear tests (see Figure 1a).

140 The parameters α and CSR_t respectively describe the steepness and the horizontal asymptote of the curve, as shown in
 141 Figure 1a,b.

142 For a regular shear stress history, κ is proportional to the number of cycles, N ; it is therefore possible to express the pore
 143 pressure ratio, r_u (ratio between the excess pore pressure and the initial effective confining pressure), as a function of the
 144 damage parameter, through the relationship proposed by Chiaradonna et al. (2016; 2018a):

$$r_u = a \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa_L} \right)^b + c \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa_L} \right)^d \quad (6)$$

145 where a , b , c and d are parameters that control the shape of the curve (Figure 1b), which can be obtained by best-fitting
 146 the data measured in cyclic laboratory tests or in-situ test results (Chiaradonna et al. 2019). It is worth noting that the
 147 parameters a and c are not independent, but they are linked each other through a limiting value of pore pressure ratio,
 148 $r_{u,lim}$, assumed as the attainment of liquefaction condition. As a matter of fact, from equation (6) it follows that: $a+c= r_{u,lim}$.
 149 Should the liquefaction criterion ideally correspond to null effective stress ratio, r_u is forced to yield unity for $N/N_L = 1$;
 150 it follows that $a + c = 1$.

152 Figure 1. (a) Cyclic resistance, (b) meaning of α in the bi-logarithmic scale and (c) excess pore pressure ratio curve

154 Alternatively to the previous methodology, but simpler, the calculation of $\Delta\sigma'_i$ is obtained by indirectly computing the r_u
 155 values through the application of the empirical relationship between r_u and the safety factor against liquefaction $FS_{liq,ff}$
 156 given by Chiaradonna & Flora (2019) and reported in Figure 2. Different $r_u - FS_{liq,ff}$ curves are provided for different soil
 157 strength, expressed as function of q_{c1Ncs} or $(N_1)_{60cs}$ (corrected blow count obtained from the SPT results), or relative
 158 density, Dr (Figure 2).

159
 160 *Figure 2. Charts with the relationship between the pore pressure ratio, r_u and the safety factor, $FS_{liq,ff}$ for different fine contents FC,*
 161 *(modified after Chiaradonna and Flora (2019)).*

162 In the latter approach, the factor of safety in free field conditions ($FS_{liq,ff}$) is defined as the ratio between the seismic
 163 loading required to trigger liquefaction and the one expected from the earthquake (Seed and Idriss, 1971). Typically, both
 164 the liquefaction resistance (capacity) and the seismic demand are written as cyclic stress ratios (respectively CRR and
 165 CSR), and the factor of safety is expressed as:

$$FS_{liq,ff} = \frac{CRR}{CSR} = \left(\frac{CRR_{M=7.5, \sigma'_v=1}}{CSR} \right) \cdot MSF \cdot K_\sigma \cdot K_\alpha \quad (7)$$

166 where $CRR_{M=7.5, \sigma'_v=1}$ is the resistance referred to a magnitude $M=7.5$ and to $\sigma'_v=103$ kPa, MSF is the magnitude scaling
 167 factor, introduced to account for the effect of the duration of the seismic event, K_σ and K_α are correcting factors to account
 168 respectively for the effective overburden stress and for an initial static shear stress on the horizontal plane. The expressions

169 of all the factors of equation (7) are not reported here for the sake of brevity, since they can be easily found in literature
170 (Idriss and Boulanger, 2006).

171 In the simplified stress-based procedure, CSR is usually expressed as:

$$CSR = 0.65 \frac{\tau_{\max}}{\sigma'_v} = 0.65 \cdot \frac{a_{\max}}{g} \cdot \frac{\sigma_v}{\sigma'_v} \cdot r_d \quad (8)$$

172 where the coefficient 0.65 is introduced to transform the irregular shear stress history (represented by τ_{\max}) in one having
173 an equivalent constant shear stress amplitude, σ_v and σ'_v are the vertical total and effective stresses at a depth z , a_{\max} is
174 the maximum horizontal acceleration, g is the gravity acceleration and r_d is a shear stress reduction factor accounting for
175 soil deformability, whose expression can be found in Boulanger and Idriss (2014).

176 To sum up, the proposed procedure for the assessment of the post-liquefaction consolidation settlement simply requires
177 the application of equation (1). The most challenging parameters to be determined are the constrained modulus and excess
178 pore water pressure induced by liquefaction. A proposed estimation of the constrained modulus is a function of the cone
179 tip resistance (equation 4), while the excess pore water pressure can be obtained by a simplified approach (calculation of
180 the safety factor in free-field conditions based on empirical charts) or a more advanced dynamic analysis (1D effective
181 stress analysis).

182 3. VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH BY CENTRIFUGE TEST

183 The described procedure is applied to a centrifuge test where liquefaction-induced settlement was accurately measured
184 (Adamidis and Madabhushi, 2016). A horizontal uniform layer of Hostun sand was created in a laminar box container.
185 The laminar box reduces boundary effects and reproduces experimentally an ideal 'free-field' condition. The model was
186 prepared by air pluviation with a targeted void ratio of 0.825.

187 Figure 3a shows the soil column at prototype scale and the location of the sensors used in the test (horizontal
188 accelerometers A, piezometers P, linear variable displacement transducer L1). The model was spun up to a centrifuge
189 acceleration of 50 g, then excited horizontally at the base with the time history of acceleration shown in Figure 3f, with
190 predominant frequency of 1 Hz (Figure 3g), at the prototype scale.

191

192 *Figure 3. Soil model (a) and vertical profile of V_s (b), q_c (c) and q_{c1Ncs} (d); normalized shear modulus and damping (e), reference*
 193 *input motion in terms of acceleration time history (f) and Fourier amplitude spectrum (g)*

194 The profile of V_s as functions of z (Figure 3b) was obtained from the correlation of Hardin and Black (1969) modified
 195 for the Hostun sand (Hoque and Tatsuoka 2004):

$$G_0 = 80 \frac{(2.17 - e)^2}{1 + e} \left(\frac{p'}{p_{ref}} \right)^{0.47} \quad (9)$$

196

197 Where e is the void ratio, p' is the mean effective stress and p_{ref} is a reference pressure value equal to the atmospheric
 198 pressure. As suggested by Adamidis and Madabhushi (2016), a profile of constant void ratio with depth was assumed
 199 before the application of the seismic action. In order to transform the relationship between the initial shear modulus, G_0
 200 and the mean effective stress, p' (equation 9) into an expression between the shear wave velocity, V_s , and the depth, z ,
 201 values of G_s and K_0 were assumed as suggested in literature (Table 1). Then, the non-linear and dissipative properties of
 202 Hostun sand were defined based on the experimental data reported by Hicher et al. (1987) and were used to calibrate the
 203 MKZ model (Figure 3e).

204 *Table 1. Physical properties of Hostun sand*

Specific gravity of the solid G_s^a	Minimum void ratio $e_{min}^{a,b}$	Maximum void ratio e_{max}^a	Friction angle φ ($^\circ$) ^{b,c}	Coefficient of earth pressure at rest K_0
2.65	0.555	1.041	33	0.46

205 ^a from Jabari and Madabhushi, 2015

206 ^b from Mitrani, 2006

207 ^c from Chian et al. 2014

208

209 A linear profile of q_c (Figure 3c) was obtained as a function of the relative density ($D_r = 0.44$) using the Kulhawy and
210 Mayne (1990) relationship for young, uncemented silica sands. A vertical profile of cone tip resistance q_{cINcs} was defined
211 (Figure 3d) according to Boulanger and Idriss (2014).

212 In order to use all these results for the numerical simulations, the ground layer has been divided into three 4 m thick
213 sublayers having a constant mean value of q_{cINcs} . Then, adopting the procedures described Chiaradonna et al. (2019) three
214 cyclic resistance and pore pressure ratio curves were defined to represent the cyclic behaviour of the three defined layers.
215 Figure 1 shows the curves for $q_{cINcs} = 21$.

216 The simulation was carried out in perfectly undrained condition; the base of the model (12 m depth at prototype scale)
217 was assumed as a rigid bedrock, and the time history of horizontal acceleration was applied without modification at the
218 base of the profile.

219 Figure 4a compares the simulated with the measured pore pressures. The measured trends indicate that soil at P7 and P3
220 depths liquefied. In the simulation, an excess pore pressure ratio, r_u , equal to 0.95 (liquefaction) is reached along the
221 whole soil column. The simulation overestimates the experimental pore pressure build-up measured at 11.40 m (P1) depth,
222 where pore pressure does not exceed 70% of the effective overburden pressure. Possible reason of discrepancy is the
223 increase with depth of the relative density that is not taken into account in the numerical model.

224 In Figure 3b, the simulated acceleration time histories are compared with the recorded signals. It can be noticed that
225 acceleration amplitudes are overestimated at the shallowest depth, particularly after liquefaction occurrence, while better
226 prediction is obtained of the deeper records. Similar considerations can be done by the comparison of the predicted
227 acceleration response spectra (Figure 4c), where the spectral acceleration around 1 s (predominant period of the input
228 signal) is overestimated at the surface, while good prediction is achieved at the other depths.

229

230 *Figure 4. Recorded and computed excess pore pressure (a) and acceleration time histories (b) and acceleration response spectra*
 231 *(5% damping) (c) along the soil column*

232 Figure 5 shows the results of the simulations in terms of vertical profile of maximum excess pore water pressure and the
 233 cone tip resistance used to calculate the constrained modulus (equation 4). Considering the expected variation of the
 234 effective stress in the re-consolidating soil, the assumed profile falls within the range of constrained modulus (0.15 - 46
 235 MPa) experimentally determined by Adamidis and Madabhushi (2016) through oedometer tests.

236 Finally, a vertical displacement of 44.5 mm was predicted at the surface of the model.

237

238 *Figure 5. Soil column and vertical profile of maximum excess pore pressure, Δu (a), cone tip resistance, q_c (b) constrained modulus,*
 239 *E_{oed} (c) and settlement, w (d)*

240 Adamidis and Madabhushi (2016) considered an adjusted time history for the free field displacement ($L1$) to take into
 241 account the effect of the LVDT plate on the overall displacement field based on the result of particle image velocimetry
 242 (PIV) analysis. According to PIV, the reconsolidation settlement was 75% of the total settlement measured by LDVT
 243 (“original LVDT” in Figure 6) during the consolidation process.

244 The proposed approach well-predicts the experimental vertical displacement ($w= 43.7$ mm), as shown in Figure 6.
 245 Nevertheless, since uncertainties still remain in the definition of the relative density of the soil, the computation has been
 246 repeated also for $Dr=40$ and 50% which leads to settlements of 51 and 35 mm (shaded area in Figure 6), respectively.

247

248 *Figure 6. Measured and computed settlement at the surface (mod. after Adamidis and Madabhushi, 2016)*

249 The prediction of the settlement has been repeated based on the pore pressure distribution obtained by the application of
 250 the relationship between the safety factor $FS_{liq,ff}$ and the excess pore pressure ratio, already described in section 2. In this
 251 case, the CSR was computed assuming the a_{max} recorded at the surface of the experiment. Figure 7 reports the vertical
 252 profiles of CRR, CSR, $FS_{liq,ff}$ and r_u . The estimated value of settlement is equal to 40.1 mm which is compatible with the
 253 observed range.

254
 255 Figure 7. Vertical profile of (a) CRR, CSR, (b) $FS_{liq,ff}$ and (c) r_u obtained by simplified approach based on r_u - $FS_{liq,ff}$ relationship.

256 4. ASSESSMENT OF FIELD CASE HISTORIES

257 The described procedure is applied to two cases in free-field conditions related to the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake, where
 258 accurate measurements of liquefaction-induced settlements are available. Both sites are the results of reclamation works
 259 where no specific soil treatments were used to densify the granular fills.

260 4.1. Treasure Island

261 Treasure Island is a 400 acre man-made island immediately northwest of the Yerba Buena Island, a rock outcrop in San
 262 Francisco Bay (Figure 8a). During the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake, liquefaction-related phenomena, including sand
 263 boils, ground surface settlements and lateral spreading movements, were evident at many locations across the island.
 264 The soils at Treasure Island may be grouped into four broad categories: the fill material (hydraulic fill), recent bay
 265 sediments (Young Bay Mud), native shoal sands (fine to medium sand) and older bay sediments (old Bay Clay) (Figure
 266 8c). Liquefaction involved the hydraulic fill, while the other layers are assumed to be not liquefiable.

267 The shear wave velocity profile was reported by Grazier (2011) based on the P-S suspension logging performed in a 122
 268 m deep downhole (Figure 8d). The bedrock depth was assumed at 88 m depth from the ground level.
 269 The EW component of the acceleration record at Yerba Buena Island was used as input motion at the base of the numerical
 270 model (Figure 8b).

271

272 *Figure 8. Treasure Island and Yerba Buena Island (black circle shows the localization of the reference soil column at fire station*
 273 *adopted in the analysis) (a), recorded motion of the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake at Yerba Buena Island (b), soil profile of Treasure*
 274 *Island (c) and V_s profile (d)*

275 For the sake of simplicity, the shear modulus degradation and damping curves were defined grouping the sand formations
 276 (hydraulic fill and sand layers) and the clayey formations (young and old clay bay). The upper bound curves proposed by
 277 Seed and Idriss (1970) were assumed for the sandy layers, while the curves obtained by laboratory tests on young bay
 278 mud samples by Sun et al. (1988) were assumed for the clayey formations (Figure 9a,b).
 279 The PWP model was calibrated on the results of a CPTU until 25 m depth from the ground level (Figure 10b) as reported
 280 by Pass (1994). Figure 9c,d show the resulting cyclic resistance and pore pressure ratio curves for hydraulic as detailed
 281 in Chiaradonna et al. (2019).

282

283 *Figure 9. Normalized shear modulus and damping ratio vs shear strain for clayey (a) and sandy (b) deposits; cyclic resistance curve*
 284 *(c) and pore pressure relationship (d) for hydraulic fill*

285 Figure 10a shows the profile of excess pore pressure ratio returned by the numerical simulation carried out in total
 286 undrained condition. The profile of constrained modulus was derived from CPTU data (Figure 10b). The constrained
 287 modulus was calculated for the liquefiable layer from equation (4) and when liquefaction is not attained (until 7 m depth)
 288 from the relationship proposed by Robertson and Cabal (2015):

$$289 \quad E_{oed} = \alpha_E \cdot (q_c - \sigma_{v0}) \quad (10)$$

290 where the coefficient is:

$$291 \quad \alpha_E = 0.0188 \left[10^{0.55I_c + 1.68} \right] \quad (11)$$

292 And I_c is the soil behaviour type index computed on the results of CPTU according to Robertson and Cabal (2015).

293 An overall settlement of about 8.7 cm was computed from the application of equation (1), which is compatible with the
 294 contour of the observed and estimated settlements (Figure 11, settlements from 10 to 20 cm).

295

296 *Figure 10. Vertical profiles of (a) excess pore pressure ratio, (b) corrected cone tip resistance and (c) constrained modulus*

297

298

299 *Figure 11. Contour of observed settlements (in cm) and estimate at the fire station (light grey triangle) (mod. after Bennett, 1998)*

300 The prediction of the settlement has been repeated based on the pore pressure distribution obtained by the application of
 301 the relationship between the safety factor $FS_{liq,ff}$ and the excess pore pressure ratio, already described in section 2. In this
 302 case the CSR was computed assuming the a_{max} recorded at the surface. Figure 12 reports the vertical profiles of CRR,
 303 CSR, $FS_{liq,ff}$ and r_u . The estimated value of settlement is equal to 14.9 mm which is compatible with the observed range.

304

305 *Figure 12. Vertical profile of (a) CRR, CSR, (b) $FS_{liq,ff}$ and (c) r_u obtained by simplified approach based on r_u - $FS_{liq,ff}$ relationship.*

306

307 **4.2. Marina District**

308 The Marina District, located on the north side of San Francisco, California, experienced significant damage during the
 309 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake even though it was more than 100 km from the epicentre (Figure 13).

310

311

Figure 13. Marina District (San Francisco)

312

In 1851, the Marina was a small embayment (Marina Cove, Figure 14a). At the time of the 1906 earthquake, Marina Cove

313

was enclosed by a rim of artificial fill (Figure 14b). In 1912, large hydraulic fills were placed in the central part of the

314

Marina (Figure 14c), and smaller fills were added until 1917.

315

316

Figure 14. Marina District in (a) 1857 (b) 1906 and (c) 1915 (modified after Bonilla, 1992)

317

The addition of all these artificial fills had important effects on the Marina District response to the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake (Bonilla, 1992), and liquefaction-induced sand boils, ground fissures, and ground settlements were observed and recorded. Most of the sand boils occurred in the area underlain by the hydraulic fill placed in 1912 (Figure 15a). Between November 3, 1989 and November 10, 1989, a USGS survey was carried out to quantify the vertical settlements caused by the earthquake (Figure 15b). Vertical settlements were calculated as the difference in elevation with a survey conducted in 1974. In so doing, the possible effects of consolidation of the fill or secondary compression of the underlain bay mud occurred in the period 1974-1989 were neglected (Bennett, 1990). Therefore, these settlements must be considered as upper bounds of the ones occurred because of the Loma Prieta earthquake.

325

No accelerometer was located in the Marina District during the earthquake. The closest site recording main-shock accelerograms was located on the bedrock in Pacific Heights, approximately 1.5 km south of the Marina District (Boatwright et al. 1992).

327

328

329 *Figure 15. Observed damage after 1989 earthquake: (a) location of sand boils (b) measured 1989-1974 settlements (in mm) over the*
 330 *1974-1961 settlements (in mm) (modified after Bennett, 1990). Grey circle shows the localization of the reference soil column*
 331 *adopted in the analysis*

332 In order to perform a dynamic analysis of a reference soil column of Marina District, the geological data reported by
 333 Bonilla (1992) were considered. Such data show that the bay area is a three-dimensional basin buried by a sequence of
 334 sedimentary deposits (Figure 16) resulting from the geologic history of the San Francisco Bay estuary. During the past
 335 million years, at least four periods of deposition occurred in San Francisco Bay, separated by periods when sea level was
 336 lower because of glaciation, and erosion of the valley occurred (Bonilla, 1992).

337 Four soil formations can be recognized in the basin on the bedrock (Figure 18b). Starting from the bottom, they are:

- 338 • Pleistocene bay deposits (silty to sandy clay), 58 m thick in the centre of the valley (Old Bay Clay);
- 339 • Pleistocene sand layer, mainly constituted by beach or dune sand; on top of this layer, there is a layer of dense
 340 sand known as "yellow hardpan", interpreted as a local boundary between Pleistocene and Holocene (Sand).
- 341 • Holocene Bay deposits (soft silty clay or clayey silt), well-known as San Francisco Bay Mud (YBM);
- 342 • Holocene beach and dune sand, clean and well-graded (Dune).

Figure 16. (a) Contour of bedrock surface and (b) section of the basin (modified after Bonilla, 1992)

343

344

345 In order to reduce the three-dimensional effects, the reference vertical soil profile for the dynamic analyses was assumed
 346 at the crossing between Cervantes Boulevard and Mallorca way, located in the centre of the basin (grey circle in Figure
 347 15b). The settlement measured in 1989 at this site was 9.6 cm.

348 At the time of the earthquake, the depth to the ground water table ranged between 2.3 and 5.5 m within the Marina District.

349 In this study, a depth of 2.9 m was considered, as reported by Bonilla (1992) at the considered location. The geotechnical
 350 profile used in the analyses is reported in Figure 17, where the shear wave velocity profile is that reported by Rollins and
 351 Mc Hood (1991).

352

353

Figure 17. (a) Soil profile (b) CPT (Bennett, 1990) and (c) V_s profiles

354

355 The stiffness degradation and damping curves for the fill and the Bay Mud are the same assumed in the Treasure Island
 356 model (Figure 9a,b). In lack of experimental data, the pore pressure model for the fill material was calibrated on the CPT
 357 profile (Figure 19b) with the procedure proposed by Chiaradonna et al. (2019), considering a fines content of 20% as
 358 reported by Rollins and McHood (1991). The curves are reported in Figure 18.

359

360 Figure 18. Hydraulic fill: (a) cyclic resistance curve (b) pore pressure relationship defined on CPT results

361 Since no recorded accelerograms were available, the E-W component of the acceleration record at Yerba Buena Island
 362 was used as input motion at the base of the numerical model (Figure 8b). Because of the uncertainties in the definition of
 363 the outcrop motion, Rollins and McHood (1991) suggested to apply it scaling the recorded PGA to 0.15g. In this study,
 364 both the measured and the (stronger) scaled accelerograms have been used.

365 Figure 19 summarizes the acceleration and excess pore pressure ratio profiles returned by the numerical simulations
 366 carried out in total undrained conditions. The constrained modulus was calculated from equation (4) for the liquefiable
 367 layer and from the relationship proposed by Robertson and Cabal (2015) when liquefaction is not attained. The computed
 368 settlements are 4.8 and 7.4 cm, respectively for the measured and scaled input motions whereas a measured value of about
 369 9.6 cm was observed.

370

371 *Figure 19. Vertical profile of maximum acceleration and excess pore pressure ratio obtained from input motion (a,b) and scaled*
 372 *input motion at 0.15g (c,d)*

373 The prediction of the settlement has been repeated based on the pore pressure distribution obtained by the application of
 374 the relationship between the safety factor $FS_{liq,ff}$ and the excess pore pressure ratio, already described in section 2. In this
 375 case, the CSR was computed assuming the a_{max} predicted at the surface by the dynamic analysis. Figure 20 reports the
 376 vertical profiles of CRR, CSR, $FS_{liq,ff}$ and r_u . The estimated value of settlement is equal to 83 mm which is compatible
 377 with the observed range.

378

379 Figure 20. Vertical profile of (a) CRR, CSR, (b) $FS_{liq,ff}$ and (c) r_u obtained by simplified approach based on r_u - $FS_{liq,ff}$ relationship.

380

381 Table 2 summarises the settlements calculated using the proposed approach, along with those obtained by using traditional
 382 semi-empirical methods, as reported by Zhang et al. (2002) on the same case histories.

383 Table 2. Comparison of the liquefaction-induced ground settlements measured and calculated using the proposed approach and
 384 traditional semi-empirical methods

Case histories	Observed settlements (cm)	Settlement with the proposed method (cm)		Settlement using Zhang et al. (2002) method (cm)
		r_u from 1D analysis	r_u from r_u - $FS_{liq,ff}$ relationship	
Centrifuge test	4.37 (Adamidis and Madabhushi, 2016)	4.45	4.01	-
Treasure Island	10 ÷ 15 (Bennett, 1998)	8.7	14.9	25.8
Marina District	< 9.6 (Bennett, 1990)	4.8 - 7.4	8.3	11.2

385

386 It is important to highlight that the observed settlements are comprehensive also of a sand ejecta component, which is not
 387 predictable by both semi-empirical methods and proposed approach. Based on photographic evidence of ejecta amounts
 388 and engineering judgment, Luque and Bray (2017) estimated values of sediment ejecta-induced settlements around 1.5 -
 389 6.0 cm during the 2010-2011 Canterbury earthquake sequence. The same order of magnitude can be likely assumed for
 390 the considered cases where widespread liquefaction evidences were observed. As consequence, the table clearly shows
 391 that, with reference to the considered case histories, the semi-empirical methods of Zhang et al. (2002) leads to an
 392 overestimation of the settlement, which is very important in the case of Treasure Island. The proposed procedure leads to

393 results systematically smaller than those of semi-empirical methods, entailing a more accurate prediction of the
394 consolidation settlements.

395 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

396 In this paper, the post-seismic consolidation settlement is calculated by simply integrating the vertical strains induced by
397 the dissipation of excess pore water pressures, calculated as suggested by Tropeano et al. (2019) or adopting the
398 relationships between r_u -FS_{liq,ff} (Chiaradonna and Flora 2019). This latter procedure is the most interesting to the reader
399 as it shows a simple-to-use way to proceed, rather than adding more sophisticated predictions. Moreover, the
400 straightforward procedure to quantify the constrained modulus needed to this aim is also suggested. The quality of the
401 prediction firstly depends on the ability to faithfully evaluate the soil response in terms of generation of excess pore water
402 pressure, which is obtained with a limited effort in terms of calculation with reference to the simplified r_u -FS_{liq,ff}
403 relationships.

404 The proposed procedure has been validated against the results of a centrifuge test where the boundary conditions were
405 such that only vertical consolidation displacements could take place upon cyclic excitation. The procedure has been then
406 successfully applied to simulate the settlements measured in two well-known and documented case histories. The
407 comparison between measured and computed settlements was in both cases satisfactory, confirming that the procedure
408 leads to a reliable prediction of the consolidation settlements. Notwithstanding the limits of the proposed approach in
409 evaluating only the volumetric settlement caused by consolidation (but most of the alternative procedures have the same
410 limitations and less accuracy), it must be stressed that it may be of help in getting (with little calculation effort) the order
411 of magnitude of the observed overall liquefaction effects at ground surface. This is not a trivial result, since even the use
412 of the most sophisticated plasticity-based advanced constitutive models implemented in commercial codes (Brinkgreve
413 et al. 2016; ITASCA 2016) may not be sufficient for a reliable estimate of post liquefaction ground settlements (Ramirez
414 et al. 2018).

415 **6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

416 This work was carried out as part of the European project Horizon 2020 – Assessment and Mitigation of liquefaction
417 potential across Europe: A holistic approach to protect structures infrastructures for improved resilience to earthquake –
418 induced liquefaction disasters – “LIQUEFACT” (grant agreement No 700748).

419 The Authors wish to thank Professor Alessandro Flora, WP4 team leader within LIQUEFACT project, for the fruitful
420 discussions and suggestions and Dr Orestis Adamidis from ETH Zurich for providing data of the OA3 centrifuge test
421 carried out at the Schofield Centre in Cambridge.

7. REFERENCES

- Adamidis O, Madabhushi GSP (2016) Post-liquefaction reconsolidation of sand. *Proc. R. Soc. A* 472: 20150745.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2015.0745>.
- Bennett MJ (1998) Sand boils and settlement on Treasure Island after the earthquake. The Loma Prieta, California, Earthquake of October 17, 1989 - Liquefaction. USGS survey professional paper 1551-B.
- Bennett MJ (1990) Ground deformation and liquefaction of soil in the Marina District. Effects of the Loma Prieta earthquake on the marina district San Francisco, California. USGS open-file Report 90-253.
- Boatwright J, Seekins LC, Fumal TE, Liu H, Mueller CS (1992) Ground-motion amplification. The Loma Prieta, California, Earthquake of October 17, 1989 - Marina District. USGS survey professional paper 1551-F.
- Bonilla MG (1992) Geologic and historical factors affecting earthquake damage. The Loma Prieta, California, Earthquake of October 17, 1989 - Marina District. USGS survey professional paper 1551-F.
- Boulanger RW, Idriss IM (2014) CPT and SPT liquefaction triggering procedures. Report No UCD/GCM-14/01, University of California at Davis, California, USA.
- Bray JD, Macedo J (2017) Simplified procedure for estimating liquefaction-induced building settlement. In *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, Seoul, Korea, 102-118 September 2017.
- Brinkgreve RBJ, Engin E, Swolfs WM (2016) PLAXIS 2D Reference Manual.
- Chian SC, Tokimatsu K, Madabhushi SPG (2014) Soil liquefaction-induced uplift of underground structures: physical and numerical modelling. *Journal Geotechnical Geoenvironmental Engineering*, ASCE, 140(10): 04014057
[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001159](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001159)
- Chiaradonna A, Flora A (2019) On the estimate of seismically-induced pore water pressure increments before liquefaction. *Geotechnique Letters* (under review)
- Chiaradonna A, Tropeano G, d'Onofrio A, Silvestri F (2016) A simplified method for pore pressure buildup prediction: from laboratory cyclic tests to the 1D soil response analysis in effective stress conditions. *Italian Conference of Researchers in Geotechnical Engineering*, CNRIG, Bologna, *Procedia Engineering*, 158: 302-307.
- Chiaradonna A, Tropeano G, d'Onofrio A, Silvestri F (2018a) Development of a simplified model for pore water pressure build-up induced by cyclic loading. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-018-0354-4>.

- Chiaradonna A, Tropeano G, d'Onofrio A, Silvestri F (2018b) Interpreting The Deformation Phenomena Of A Levee Damaged During The 2012 Emilia Earthquake. Special Issue of Soil Dynamic and Earthquake Engineering, SDEE, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2018.04.039>
- Chiaradonna A, Flora A, d'Onofrio A, Bilotta E (2019) A Pore Water Pressure Model Calibration Based On In-Situ Test Results. *Soils and Foundations* (under review).
- Cubrinovski M, Rhodes A, Ntritsos N, van Ballegooy S (2018) System Response of Liquefiable Deposits. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2018.05.013>
- Ghosh B, Madabhushi SPG (2002) An efficient tool for measuring shear wave velocity in the centrifuge." Proc. Int. Conf. on Phys. Modelling in Geotechnics, R. Phillips, P. J. Guo, and R. Popescu, eds., Balkema, Rotterdam, Netherlands, 119–124.
- Graizer V (2011) Treasure Island geotechnical array – case study for site response analysis. In Proceedings of the 4th IASPEI/IAEE International Symposium: Effects of surface geology on seismic motion, University of California Santa Barbara, California, USA.
- Hardin BO, Black WL (1969) Closure to vibration modulus of normally consolidated clays. *J Soil Mech Found Div* 95(SM6):1531–1537.
- Hicher PY, El Hosri MS, Homsy M (1987) Cyclic properties of soils within a large range of strain amplitude. In *Soil dynamics and liquefaction*. Editor A.S. Cakmak. Elsevier co-published with Computational mechanics publications.
- Hoque E, Tatsuoka F (2004) Effects of stress ratio on small-strain stiffness during triaxial shearing. *Geotechnique* 54(7):429–439.
- Ishihara K, Yoshimine M (1992) Evaluation of settlements in sand deposits following liquefaction during earthquakes. *Soils and Foundations*, 32(1): 173–188.
- ITASCA Consulting Group Inc. (2016) *FLAC 8.0 - Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua*. Minneapolis, MN, US.
- Iwasaki T, Arakawa T, Tokida K (1984) Simplified Procedures for Assessing Soil Liquefaction During Earthquakes. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 3(1):49–58.
- Jabary RN, Madabhushi SPG (2015) Tuned mass damper effects on the response of multi-storied structures observed in geotechnical centrifuge tests. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 77: 373-380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2015.06.013>
- Kulhawy FH, Mayne PW (1990) Manual on estimating soil properties for foundation design. Report EL-6800, Electric Power Research Institute, Palo Alto, 306 p. www.epri.com.

- Luque R, Bray JD (2017) Dynamic Analyses of Two Buildings Founded on Liquefiable Soils during the Canterbury Earthquake Sequence *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, ASCE, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001736](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001736)
- Marcuson WF III, Hynes ME, Franklin AG (1990). Evaluation and use of residual strength in seismic safety analysis of embankments. *Earthquake Spectra* 6(3): 529-572.
- Matasovic. N, Vucetic M (1993) Cyclic characterization of liquefiable sands. *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, ASCE, 119(11):1805-1822.
- Meyerhof GG, Fellenius BH (1985) *Canadian Foundation Engineering Manual*, 2nd edition. Canadian Geotechnical Society.
- Mitrani H (2006) Liquefaction remediation techniques for existing buildings. Ph.D. dissertation, Cambridge Univ., Cambridge, U.K.
- Pass DG (1994) Soil characterization of the soil of the deep accelerometer site at Treasure Island, San Francisco, California. Master Degree Thesis, University of New Hampshire.
- Phillips C, Hashash YMA (2009) Damping formulation for non linear 1D site response analyses. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 29(7): 1143–1158.
- Ramirez J, Barrero AR, Chen L, Dashti S, Ghofrani A, Taiebat M, Arduino P (2018) Site Response in a Layered Liquefiable Deposit: Evaluation of Different Numerical Tools and Methodologies with Centrifuge Experimental Results. *J Geotech Geoenv Eng* 04018073-1 [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001947](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001947)
- Robertson PK, Cabal (Robertson) KL (2015) *Guide to Cone Penetration Testing for Geotechnical Engineering*. Gregg Drilling & Testing, Inc.
- Rollins KM, McHood MD (1991) Comparison of computed and measured liquefaction-induced settlements in the Marina District, San Francisco. The Loma Prieta, California, Earthquake of October 17, 1989 - Liquefaction. USGS survey professional paper 1551-B.
- Santisi d'Avila M.P., Lenti L., Semblat J.F. (2012) Modelling strong seismic motion: 3D loading path vs wavefield polarization. *GJI*, 190, pp.1607-1624.
- Santisi d'Avila M.P., Semblat J.F., Lenti L. (2013) Strong Ground Motion in the 2011 Tohoku Earthquake: A One-Directional Three-Component Modeling, *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, pp. 1394-1410, vol. 103 No. 2B
- Seed HB, Idriss IM (1970) Soil moduli and damping factors for dynamic response analysis. Report No EERC 70-10, University of California, Berkeley, California, USA.

- Sun JI, Golesorkhi R, Seed HB (1988) Dynamic moduli and damping ratios for cohesive soils. Report No UCB/EERC-88/15. University of California at Berkeley.
- Tokimatsu K, Seed HB (1987) Evaluation of settlements in sands due to earthquake shaking. *Journal of Geotechnical and Engineering, ASCE*, 113(8): 861–878.
- Tropeano G, Chiaradonna A, d’Onofrio A, Silvestri F (2016) An innovative computer code for 1D seismic response analysis including shear strength of soils, *Géotechnique*, 66(2):95-105.
- Tropeano G, Chiaradonna A, d’Onofrio A, Silvestri F (2019) Numerical model for non-linear coupled analysis on seismic response of liquefiable soils. *Computers and Geotechnics* 105: 211-227.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2018.09.008>
- Zhang G, Robertson PK, Brachman RWI (2002) Estimating liquefaction-induced ground settlements from CPT for level ground. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 39: 1168–1180.